

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Effects of Emigration on Rural Labor Markets"

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ABSTRACT

We prioritized the paper “Effects of Emigration on Rural Labor Markets”^[1] because of its potential relevance to the decision to shut down the charity “No Lean Season”. Although we normally seek two or more strong evaluations, we struggled to find evaluators for this paper. We would have persisted further, but we were also advised that other work in this area seems more relevant (see discussion below). Thus we decided to release this package with only a single evaluation.

Evaluation

1. [Frank Gyimah Sackey’s evaluation](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment: We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.”

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5):¹ On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#).) *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Frank Gyimah Sackey’s evaluation	70	2.5

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).²

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.³

Evaluation summary

Frank Gyimah Sackey⁴

The paper sought to examine the effects of emigration on rural labour markets, specifically, how outmigration transforms rural labour markets [using an experiment involving a transport subsidy intervention]. Using a sample of 5,792 potential seasonal migrants across 133 villages, the authors observed that transport subsidies increased beneficiaries’ income [and this] generated spillover effects. The research findings indicate that the

transport subsidies increase beneficiaries' income due to better employment opportunities and also generated some spillovers [These included] increasing individual take-up rate as a result of a higher density offers which induces those connected to the offered recipients to also migrate, the village emigration rate increases, increase in the male agriculture wage rate in the village increasing income earned in the village. [...] There is a decrease in the price of non-tradeables such as prepared food and tea while net food prices increase. The paper contributes immensely to the research on migration and labour studies. It also provides practical insights on intervention and adds useful value to research on interventions and has policy implications. The immense contribution is attributed to policy implications of the effects of subsidies on intervention and how the impact positively on such interventions. The practical insight is demonstrated by how recipients receive such interventions when they are directly involved and whatever benefits such as the subsidies go to them directly to achieve the desired results.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator		
	Frank Gyimah Sackey		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁵	70	(50, 90)	6
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	70	(50, 90)	8
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁹	70	(50, 90)	10
Logic & communication ¹¹	70	(50, 90)	12
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹³	70	(50, 90)	14
Real-world relevance ¹⁵	70	(50, 70)	16

Relevance to global priorities ¹⁷	70	(50, 90)	18
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Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator		
	Frank Gyimah Sackey		
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	2.5	(1.0, 3.0)	19
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	2.5	(1.0, 3.0)	
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 		

Evaluation manager's discussion

Evidence Action shut down the charity No Lean Season (the precise intervention in this paper) partly because of "Mixed evidence of impact" (see [GiveWell's report here](#)). But the decision was also partly due to particular problems (allegations of fraud and mismanagement by the implementing partner. Thus, we suspected there may still be a strong case that this could be a cost-effective intervention. The present paper reported substantial positive effects, and was heavily cited. Thus we believed it deserved more careful evaluation, and if there were substantial flaws, these should be publicly shared.

Although we normally seek two or more strong evaluations, we struggled to find evaluators who could provide informed constructive criticism and appraisal. We might have persisted further, however...

After further consultation with an applied researcher in this area, we were advised that the GiveWell's decision was more about issues having to do with the failure of the program to *scale up*, rather than its earlier performance as considered in the paper evaluated here. Follow-on work thus seems more relevant for further evaluation, such as "Delegation Risk and Implementation at Scale: Evidence from a Migration Loan Program in Bangladesh" (Mitchell et al, 2023) [2]. [20](#)

Author engagement

On June 26 2024 the authors let us know they are working on a revised version of the present paper, and hope to respond to the current evaluation when the revised version is released. We may revisit this work at that point, with potential for further evaluation.

References

[1] Akram, Agha Ali, Shyamal Chowdhury, and Ahmed Mushfiq Mobarak. *Effects of emigration on rural labor markets*. No. w23929. National Bureau of Economic Research, 2017.

Footnotes

1. See "1 Mar 2024 note" above. [↵](#)
2. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
3. See "1 Mar 2024 note" above. See [here](#) to learn how this changed, and to see the earlier instructions. [↵](#)
4. Managers' note: we made some small typographical edits to the evaluator's text. [↵](#)
- 5.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

6. The paper sought to examine the effects of emigration on rural labor markets, specifically, how outmigration transforms rural labor markets through the subsidized transport cost as an intervention mechanism in its experimental approach. Using a sample of 5,792 potential seasonal migrants across 133 villages, authors observed that transport subsidies increased beneficiaries' income that generate spill-over effects. The paper contributes immensely to the research on migration and migration and labor studies. [↵](#)
- 7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

└

8. The paper provides practical insights on interventions and adds useful value to research on interventions.

└

9. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? └

10. Though the author found no usefulness in determining whether the migration experience of those travelling from high intensity village is more successful than those from low intensity village between migrants and non-migrants, this could have been observed with migrants alone. └

11. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? └

12. The author also could have examined differences in individual endowments among the migrants and non-migrants as the willingness to migrate may be determined by individual characteristics and not the transport subsidy alone. Again, comparison between those who are offered subsidies and those who were not should have included decomposition and counterfactual analysis as well as measuring the wage gap among them to critically examine the push factors apart from using the transport subsidy as a sole factor. └

13.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

└

14. The sources of the data are clear, while the analyses are well explained with clear labelling. Replicating the analysis is possible, however, the modeling and the analysis is so broad that one might lose focus, in relation to the objectives. └

15.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

↵

16. The paper is very relevant to the real-world situation while its policy implications are consistent and implementable. Though the set-up assumptions are valid, the literature review leading to the assumptions should have had the Harris-Todaro theory and model on rural migration was adequately reviewed with its assumptions to add more insights to the set-up assumptions. Again, the analysis, especially, regarding the result tables were too many that the average audience may lose focus. Though some of the tables have been placed as an appendix there is the need to streamline and summarize the models and the tables in a brief but in a parsimonious manner in order to lose important results. ↵

17. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? ↵

18. Though the topic is clearly explained, useful to the global audience and has high impact interventions, the author may consider using the word "Impact" instead of "Effects." ↵

19. Top B-journal/Strong field journal ↵

20. Mobarak also wrote [a nontechnical comment](#)[1] about the difficulties of scaling up interventions (largely based on his experience here), ↵

References

1. Akram, A. A., Chowdhury, S., & Mobarak, A. M. (2017). *Effects of Emigration on Rural Labor Markets*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w23929> ↵
2. Mitchell, H., Mobarak, A. M., Naguib, K., Reimão, M. E., & Shenoy, A. (2023). Delegation risk and implementation at scale: Evidence from a migration loan program in Bangladesh. *Unpublished Manuscript*. https://Ashishenoy.Github.io/Website/Paper_NLS_Evaluation.Pdf. ↵
3. Akram, Agha Ali, Shyamal Chowdhury, and Ahmed Mushfiq Mobarak. *Effects of emigration on rural labor markets*. No. w23929. National Bureau of Economic Research, 2017. ↵